

SARS-CoV-2 evolution and COVID-19 impacts on socioeconomics of Pakistan-a mini review

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ABSTRACT

Coronaviruses in humans were first found in the 1960s from the United Kingdom. “SARS-CoV”, “HCoV NL63”, “HCoV” “HKU1” in 2004, “MERS-CoV” in 2013, and “SARS-CoV-2” in 2019 are discovered. The education sector and industries of Pakistan as well as world is badly affected by COVID-19. There are over 2 crore 7.3 million peoples are unemployed during corona lockdown. Sports have also been affected by covid-19. People should follow rule to save their lives and maintain a good hygiene.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS, MER-CoV, Education, Unemployment

INTRODUCTION

Coronaviruses in humans were first documented in the 1960s from United Kingdom (Mahase, 2020). Coronaviruses have spike projections and are single-stranded RNA viruses. Two coronaviruses outbreaks observed earlier before SARS-CoV-2. Coronaviruses belong to family Coronaviridae, the subfamily Coronavirinae and belong to four genera “*Alphacoronaviruses*”, “*Betacoronaviruses*”, “*Gammacoronaviruses*” and “*Deltacoronaviruses*”. Two coronaviruses are “Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus” (abbreviated as SARS-COV) and the “Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus” (abbreviated as MERS-COV) documented at two different times (Kaur *et al.*, 2020). Coronaviruses causes infections viz. digestive and respiratory sicknesses. Lungs problems can damages like pneumonia. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome is a affects people in the Middle East (MERS-CoV) (Tidona and Darai, 2011; Altaf, 2020; ScientificAmerican, 2020).

Pneumonia was observed from China and cause of pneumonia is diagnosed due to SARS-Cov-2 (Adil, 2021). Coronaviruses mode of transmission is aerosol COVID-19, SARS-CoV (Shereen *et al.*, 2020), “*Avian coronavirus*” (Cavanagh, 2007) and “*Murine coronavirus*” (Weiss and Navas-Martin, 2005). SARS-Cov-2 was documented as unique coronavirus and genetically it is more related with SARS-like coronaviruses. Scientists also noted that “SARS-Cov-2” is not-mosaic having about half of its genome of a lineage within the “*Betacoronavirus*”. These genomic features showed their high virulence in human being (Jiang *et al.*, 2020; Paraskevis *et al.*, 2020; Wu *et al.*, 2020; Xu *et al.*, 2020).

COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACT ON EDUCATION

The effect of pandemic COVID-19 is noted in all parts of glob. The education department of Pakistan and whole glob is affected badly by this. The education department has affected very much cause of outbreak of COVID-19. Schools, colleges and universities classes have been

eliminated and exams were postponed and admission processes were delayed. Placements for students' may also be affected with companies delaying on the board of students. Primary and secondary classes have been promoted in next classes and higher classes exams have been postponed for a long time due to COVID-19. COVID-19 has proffered of recent technologies to convey knowledge and information. The COVID-19 pandemic condition encouraged societies to study and utilize digital technology and outcome in enhancing the digital literacy (Umair, 2020; Martín *et al.*, 2021; Pokhrel and Chhetri, 2021). COVID-19 pandemic produced negative effects on students of Pakistan. Higher Education System (HEC) failed to provide the education facilities to all students (Zahra *et al.*, 2020).

COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACT ON SOCIOECONOMICS

The current pandemic of (COVID-19) continues to affect the human life in Pakistan. In the present circumstance, the following are particularly affected: viz. almost fifty percent agriculture and livestock, approximately 22% wage labor, approximately 62% of daily wage, 33% on farming, livestock, fishing and agricultural labor and 29% on non-agricultural labor (UNDP, 2020).

Figure 1: Annual GDP in Pakistan and COVID-19 impact on GDP of Pakistan.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACT ON GDP

The GDP in Pakistan extended 0.5 percent in 2020, listed a development of one percent in the earlier time. Real “Gross Domestic Product” development figure in the country of Pakistan is developed annually, accessible between 2001 and 2020, with 4.5 percent an average rate. The figure arrived at whole era the highest of 7.5 percent in 2004 and a document the lowest of 0.5 percent in 2020. CEIC documented real “Gross Domestic Product” GDP (Figure 1). The “Pakistan Bureau of Statistics” gives real “Gross Domestic Product”, at chain linked from 2005 to 2006 prices. In the latest documentation, Nominal “Gross Domestic Product” of Pakistan, in 2020 arrived at 264.1 US dollar bn. Its “Gross Domestic Product” deflator enhanced 9.3 percent in 2020. The “Gross Domestic Product” Per Capita in Pakistan achieved 1,321.3 US dollar in Jun 2019. Its “Gross Savings Rate” GSR was measured at 8.4 percent in 2020. For Nominal “Gross Domestic Product” investment, contributions measured for 15.4 percent in 2020. “Private

Consumption” PC was noted for 78.5 percent in 2020. The “Public Consumption” was documented for 13.1 percent in 2020 (CEIC, 2021).

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